

THE ROLE OF HAZRAT YUSUF HAMADANI'S SPIRITUAL HERITAGE IN EDUCATION AND UPBRINGING OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract: Man in life own place to find, two the world to his happiness the achievement of the country development contribution to add and that's it to the motherland worthy one a child to be without education imagination by doing it won't be. This is what we do two wing if not to the sky rising to the sky flight do it that he didn't get it in comparison will be Education about word when he left , Abdulla Avlani's " Education for us ". either life - yes death, yes salvation - yes crash , happiness - yes disaster is an issue ," he said deep meaningful opinion remember falls. Great enlightened our grandfather's this words our century At the beginning of our nation for how many important has been if, the present at the same time , perhaps more than that current important have _ Due to independence, our spiritual heritage began to emerge. Educating the young generation is becoming one of our main goals.

Keywords: Education, Hazrat Yusuf Hamadani, Great enlightened, universal human values.s

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It is the honorable duty of every mature person to form high spiritual thinking in young people. Therefore, the development of our new society, which is being built, will be built on the basis of highly spiritual individuals. No matter how well-educated and knowledgeable any advanced specialist is, he should embody national, universal human values and high spirituality. As stated by the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. Karimov: The ideology of national independence built on the basis of centuries-old traditions, customs, language and spirit of our people, combined with universal human values, instills a sense of confidence in the future in the hearts and minds of people. it should serve to educate them in the spirit of love for the Motherland, humanitarianism, honesty, bravery and patience, a sense of happiness, and a desire for knowledge and enlightenment ²²⁸.

Every society dreams of raising a generation that is mature, matured in all aspects, and combines all positive and noble qualities. The unique heritage of our people today gives great spiritual strength to the young generation . Today, preservation of our historical and cultural heritage and its wide application in the education of the young generation is one of the main tasks ²²⁹. The legacy of Yusuf

²²⁸ IA Karimov. *Uzbekistan economic reforms deepening on the way* - Tashkent : Uzbekistan , volume 3 , 1996 . - 2 83

²²⁹ <https://xs.uz/uzkr/post/confirmation-of-the-concept-of-millij-culture-in-the-respublika-of-uzbekistan>

Hamadani , a great figure of Sufism, plays an important role in the education of young people today. Yusuf Hamadani (1048-1140) was born in the city of Hamadan, Iran. He came to Khorezm in the 14th century and became a sheikh. Yusuf Hamadani's full name is Abu Yaqub Yusuf ibn Husayn ibn Ayyub Hamadani. Yusuf Hamadani died in Bayram Ali district of Turkmenistan while returning to his homeland and was buried there. The current mausoleum of Yusuf Hamadani in Shavat district is considered to be the place of his footsteps. Hazrat Yusuf Hamadani's mausoleum has become one of the holiest shrines for Khorezm residents today. Khorezm Regional Cultural Heritage Department attached to "Waqf" charitable public fund on the basis of the right of operational management on the basis of a free use contract. This mausoleum is according to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 846 of October 4, 2019_mainly immovable objects of Tangible cultural heritage included in the national list ²³⁰.

Hazrat Yusuf Hamadani 's main goal in his work is to be in the circle of murid-disciples, to educate them, rather than to create scientific and educational works. That is why his house was called "Kaba of Khurasan". Yusuf Hamadani is famous for having trained many students due to his enthusiasm in the field of education. During this period, Khoja Yusuf Hamadani brought up Khoja Abdullah Barqi, Khoja Husan Andioqib, slave Khoja Ahmad Yassavi and Khoja Abduholiq G'ijduvani.

Yusuf Hamadani , the works of Abdukholiq Ghijduvani, Farididin Attar, Abdurahman Jami, Alisher Navoi contain information about his personality, exemplary life in terms of education.

Khoja Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani's work titled "Maqamoti Yusuf Hamadani" written in Persian gives detailed information about Sheikh Yusuf Hamadani's portrait and manner, good manners, behavior, prayer, life activities and attitude to his students. He also calls on the members of the sect to learn from Yusuf Hamadani's exemplary lifestyle. In the work "Maqamoti Yusuf Hamadani", Sheikh Hamadani was very pure, pious, honest and pious, and he demanded the same from others. He could not agree with injustice, hypocrisy, and hypocrisy. For example, it is said in "Maqamot": "...They (Yusuf Hamadani) hated liars, selfish, bribe-takers, braggarts, tyrants, unjust bloodshed, tyrants. They used to invite scoundrels, bribe-takers, slanderers, evil-doers, those who hide the Sharia to gain prestige, and other hypocrites, and make them ask for forgiveness and repent. If they didn't obey, our sheikh would chase them away from their presence and consider them as their enemies. They often ate coarse food and ate little water and bread. They did not curse anyone, did not use insulting words like "pig", "dog", "beggar", "dog", "damn you" and did not curse anyone... ²³¹".

²³⁰<https://lex.uz/ru/docs/4543266?ONDATE2=14.07.2022&action=compare>

²³¹<https://hidayat.uz/>

In his famous philosophical work "Mantiq ut-Tayr" Fariduddin Attar describes Yusuf Hamadoni as follows: "Imam of the livelihood of the Tariqat, the owner of the secrets of the soul, the creator of goodness and goodness ²³². "

In Abdurrahman Jami's work "Nafahot ul-uns min hazarot il-quds" ("The Breezes of Friendship Blowing from the Holy Ones"), he gave information about Yusuf Hamadani and said, "A scientist, a scholar, owner of status, great gifts, blessings and they were ²³³the owners of the authorities.

Alisher Navoi gave information about Yusuf Hamadani in his book "Nasayim-ul Muhabbat": "Yusuf Hamadani's status and merits were amazing and limitless. There were an incomparable number of disciples and devotees. Khwaja Yusuf Hamadani's sects were openly mentioned."

So, in conclusion, we should emphasize that we will have to make good use of the legacy of the great people who lived in our distant past, as well as universal human values. After all, the foundation for the future begins with self-awareness and patriotism.

In conclusion, it can be said that the appropriate use of the spiritual heritage of ancestors in the process of education and upbringing is an important means of educating highly spiritual individuals.

²³² Fariduddin Actor . Logic ut-tair . Prose ba è n. Enter the word and from Persian translation _ N. Komilov , M. Mahmudov . T.: Ghafur Ghulam in the name of edition è t- printing press creative house , 2006. - 173 p

²³³<https://hidayat.uz/30062>